

Online Monitoring of Metal Oxides in Molten Fluoride Electrolytes

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Abstract

Reliable monitoring of oxide concentrations in electrowinning of metals in fluoride-based electrolytes is very important for avoiding unwanted reactions, notably perfluorocarbons emissions which are very potent greenhouse gases. A probe, consisting of a working electrode and a counter electrode, has been developed for online monitoring of metal oxide concentrations in molten fluoride electrolytes. During measurements, the immersed probe in the electrolyte is subject to fast anodic polarisation sweeps while electric current response is recorded. During anodic polarisation, oxide species in the electrolyte are rapidly depleted at the probe, resulting in a response called anode effect on the probe tip, triggering a rapid voltage increase and current drop. The rate of oxide depletion and the consequent anode effect is proportional to the dissolved oxide concentration. This allows to correlate voltage-current-time curves to the oxide concentration. Measurements in cryolite melts with different oxide concentrations showed different voltages at which anode effect occurs.

Introduction

The global annual production of aluminium in 2022 was 68.5 million tonnes [1]. Production of aluminium is an energy intensive process responsible for significant emissions of greenhouse gasses to the atmosphere. Greenhouse gas emissions from the production of aluminium arise from the various reactions occurring. The production of primary aluminium is based on molten salt electrolysis using consumable carbon anodes. These consumable carbon anodes partake in the aluminium producing reactions to produce CO₂ as shown Equation 1 below.

Equation 1 suggests that 1.22 tonnes of CO₂ is produced for every tonne of aluminium produced, however, the actual value is higher due to factors such as air burn, loss in current efficiency, Boudouard reaction, dusting, etc. The average industrial value is ca. 1.5 tonne CO₂ per tonne Al [1,2]. In addition, the production of primary aluminium generates significant amount of perfluorocarbon (PFC) emissions, mainly CF₄ and C₂F₆, as illustrated by Equations 2 and 3. These gases are very potent greenhouse gases with large detrimental effect on our atmosphere. The average PFC emissions for the aluminium industry in 2022 was estimated to be 0.7 tCO₂eq./t Al [1].

The emission of PFCs is mainly related to problems with controlling the alumina concentration in the electrolyte, leading to a phenomenon called anode effect [3]. An anode effect is an unwanted condition at the electrode induced by insufficient amount of dissolved oxides, alumina, in the electrolyte. It causes an increase of cell voltage, inactivate some areas of the electrodes, and triggers undesirable anodic reactions as given by Equations 2 and 3 resulting in the emission of the PFC gases. Since the anode effects are related to process control issues, i.e. alumina feeding and distribution, they can in theory be avoided entirely with proper feed control, thereby eliminating PFC emissions from aluminium production.

Dissolution of alumina in the molten cryolite-based electrolyte is one of the most complex aspects of the electrolysis process as many parameters are involved. Firstly, during electrolysis, oxide concentration in the bath is usually kept as low as possible, just to provide an appropriate concentration to maintain a stable process [2,3]. This ensures a high dissolution rate for each addition of alumina, usually around 1-2 kg alumina batches [2,3], minimising sludge formation. On the other hand, it creates a delicate balance between appropriate process conditions and the unwanted anode effects.

Operating at the low oxide concentrations cause several challenges, especially the oxide distribution within the cell since feeding is limited to a few point feeders. This issue becomes even more challenging for larger cells with larger anodes as these are more prone to so called partial anode effects [4]. Oxide distribution is directly connected to electrolyte stirring conditions (magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) effects) and feeding arrangement in the cell [3]. Also, the microstructure, particle size distribution, impurity content, etc. have large impact on dissolution kinetics. Moreover, since quality of raw materials is rarely fixed in the long term, the industry needs to adapt to alumina quality variations and optimise feeding strategy accordingly. Therefore, knowledge about dissolution kinetics of oxide materials is important for making good predictions of the performance of the electrolysis process, both to control and to tune the production appropriately. Several researchers have over the years tried different analytical techniques for continuous monitoring of the oxide concentration [5, 6,7,8,9,10]. The most employed techniques by of researchers are based on electrochemical response measurements. The measurements involve applying a

rapid voltage sweep to an electrode assembly immersed in a fluoride electrolyte by means of a voltage-controlled source of electric power. By monitoring the current passing through the electrode assembly during each sweep, the voltage and current at which anode effect is induced is recorded. The voltage at which the anode effect occurs is observed to vary with the concentration of oxides in the electrolyte. Haverkamp et. al. [7], observed that the potential at which anode effect occurs increases with increasing oxide concentration. It is thus possible to correlate the oxide concentration with the applied potential at anode effect within a defined range of parameters. This makes the voltammetry technique suitable for determining oxide concentration in fluoride melts when appropriate calibrations are done.

The present paper describes the development of a sensor for in-situ monitoring of oxide concentration in molten fluoride salts. Besides analytical methods for oxide concentration analysis such as inert gas fusion technique and XRD, that requires sampling and sample preparations, there is no existing, commercially available method for in-situ measurements of the oxide concentration in molten fluoride salts. The presented sensor is based on the theory described in the patent by R.G. Haverkamp et al. [7].

Experimental

Presented results were carried out using setup shown in the Figure 1. Electrolyte with volume approx. 450 cm³ was melted in graphite crucible placed in vertical tube furnace with resistive heating element. Three different electrolyte type were used: conventional industrial cryolite bath (NaF-AlF₃-CaF₂-Al₂O₃), low temperature cryolite bath (NaF-AlF₃-KF-Al₂O₃) and rare earth metal fluoride (NdF₃-PrF₃-LiF-Nd₂O₃-Pr₂O₃). The first bath type was prepared from frozen industrial electrolyte with CR = NaF/AlF₃ = 2.1, 5 wt% CaF₂, and ca. 1 wt% Al₂O₃. The low temperature cryolite melt had a CR = (NaF+KF)/AlF₃ = 1.3, KR (potassium fluoride ratio) = KF/(NaF+KF) = 0.8 and prepared using NaF (Merck, 99.9 wt%), KF (Merck, 99.9 wt%), and AlF₃ (in-house sublimated, > 99 %). Rare earth metal electrolyte was prepared from 88.58 wt% of NdF₃ (in-house, 98 %) and 11.42 wt% LiF (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.9 %). Temperature of bath was 980, 808 and 1048 °C for conventional, low temperature, and rare earth metals bath, respectively, and it was monitored during experiment using shielded thermocouple immersed in the bath.

Figure 1 Setup for monitoring oxide concentration. a) Experimental setup; (1) thermocouple; (2) oxide feeding tube; (3) graphite crucible; (4) electrolyte (molten salt); (5) stirrer; (6) measuring probe. b) In-house measuring unit for generating and recording electrochemical responses.

Aluminium oxide (Merck, 99.9 wt%) was added to the conventional and low temperature bath using a stainless-steel feeding tube in batches corresponding to 0.5 or 2.5 wt% of the total bath mass. For rare earth metal bath, a mixture of 77.5 wt% of Nd₂O₃ (Alfa Aesar, 99.9%) and 22.5 wt% of Pr₂O₃ (Alfa Aesar, 99.9%) was used. During the test, the bath was agitated using a boron nitride stirring element. The default stirring speed was 120 rpm, if not specified differently. The measuring probe was immersed in the bath and kept at the same position during the whole test. Immersed part of probe is depicted in Figure 2 b and consists of two electrodes: a working electrode in the form of a small area conical tip and a larger area counter electrode. The probe contains a built-in thermocouple to monitor probe temperature, this could be useful in short term field measurements as it will help know if the probe has been in the melt long enough for representative data. The probe was connected to the in-house built measuring unit (shown in Figure 1b), responsible for generating a driving polarisation signal, and for recording the probe voltage (potential difference between probe electrodes) and probe current. The measuring unit can generate fast polarisation signals for the probe with sweep rate up to 50 kV/s and maximum current and voltage up to 20 A and 15 V correspondingly. Polarisation signal can be voltage or current controlled and can have user-programmed shape: linear sweeps or square wave pulses. In this work, the focus is on the use of linear voltage sweeps which is the signal type originally proposed by Haverkamp et al. [7], however, utilizing other type of signal can enhance the probe response performance. The sample rate of signal recording was 100 kHz for all presented results. The relationship between the probe response signal and the oxide concentration in the bath is a non-linear curve which must be experimentally calibrated. A polynomial fitting is utilised to calculate a transfer function from the non-linear curve to translate the probe response data to oxide concentration values. The probe response and the corresponding transfer function is not universal and must thus be determined for

different electrolyte systems. To approximate the oxide concentration using the probe response, ex-situ oxide concentration analysis of bath samples collected during the experiments was performed by analysing the oxygen content using the inert gas fusion technique with the LECO TC-436 DR (Leco Corp., USA) instrument.

Results and Discussion

Figure 2a shows typical polarisation curves of the probe produced by applying fast voltage sweeps in the anodic direction for fluoride electrolytes containing 2 and 7 wt% of Al_2O_3 . In the first stage of both cases, the current increases quite linearly with applied voltage until a rapid drop is observed which manifests anode effect occurrence at the probe tip. During anodic polarisation, oxygen from oxyfluoride ions (formed from alumina and the fluoride species) is removed forming CO/CO_2 gas at the anode as shown by the schematic reaction given by Equation 4.

Oxyfluoride species can form different complexes with different Al, O and F ratios depending on oxide concentrations and acidity of electrolyte. There are more possible oxyfluoride complexes that exist in electrolyte, however, these in Equation 4 are generally accepted in literature as the most stable and common ones [11-13]. Once all the oxyfluoride ions in the probe vicinity are depleted, a passive layer resulting from the decomposition of the fluoride species in the probe vicinity to form PFCs as shown by Equations 2 and 3 above occur. The passive layer causes a passivation of the probe tip which results in blockage or hindrance of current flow described as anode effect [3]. There is a substantial difference between polarisation curves recorded at different alumina content as presented in Figure 2a. In case of the electrolyte containing 2 wt% of alumina, the probe passivation occurred at 2.9 A and 3.9 V while for 7 wt% these values were much larger: 15.4 A and 10.4 V, respectively. They are called the critical current density and the critical voltage. Intuitively, the lower concentration of dissolved oxide in electrolyte, the quicker the oxide depletion occurs during voltage sweeps. This large difference in polarisation curves of the probe depending on alumina concentration allows to correlate probe response with alumina concentration and it is the basis of described method. It is worth noting that the values of critical voltage and current in Figure 2 are not specific for any electrolyte concentration. Besides the strong dependence on oxide concentration, they response also depend on the electrical resistance between the electrodes in the probe. In addition, since depletion and passivation processes are dependent on ion transport which in turn is a time dependent process, the sweep rate of polarisation hugely affects the shape of curve.

Figure 2 a) Polarisation curves of probe at different Al_2O_3 concentration in an electrolyte using voltage sweep rate 5000 V/s. b) Schematic of probe.

The effect of resistance can be minimised by using a fixed electrode arrangement in the probe. Moreover, by using the electric charge passed through the probe until passivation is reached instead of the critical voltage or the critical current will eliminate the effect of inter-polar resistance. Since transport of oxide species in vicinity of the probe tip is mainly driven by diffusion, the large dependence of charge required to induce anode effect and polarisation sweep rate is expected for different oxide contents.

Figure 3 a) Current response curves of probe polarised at different voltage sweep rates. Numbers next to each curve show charge (integrated shaded area under curve). b) Dependence of polarisation sweep rate on charge-to-passivation.

The graph in Figure 3a presents current response of the probe during linear polarisation at different sweep rates, from 100 to 10000 V/s. Shaded area under the curves indicates charge which was passed through the probe until the passivation occurred. These plots clearly illustrate how significantly the charge-to-passivation value changes with voltage sweep rate applied to the probe. The faster sweep rate results in decrease of charge required to reach passivation of the probe. For the sweep rate 100 V/s, the probe was passivated after passing 46.6 mC while for 10000 V/s after only 3.1 mC. Time to passivation was also decreased substantially, from 37 ms to almost 1 ms. Smaller charge required to passivate the probe is beneficial due to reduced time for single measurement. In addition, it translates into less tip consumption and longer lifetime of the probe.

Stirring of the bath has a strong influence on passivation of the probe, however, this effect is only visible at low alumina concentrations. The graph in Figure 4 shows the effect of electrolyte stirring on charge-to-passivation of the probe. At 2 wt% of alumina in the electrolyte, faster stirring significantly increases the value of charge making it more difficult to trigger passivation of the probe. Interestingly, at high oxide concentration, this effect is minimal suggesting that at such conditions the diffusion is more important than the convection for ion transport. This observation may indicate a great impact of even moderate stirring on decreasing anode effects occurrence since industrial process operates at low alumina concentrations.

Figure 4 Effect of sweep rate, oxide concentration and stirring speed on mean charge-to-passivation of the probe tip.

The presented probe has been tested in different molten salt systems including rare earth fluoride melts (e.g., neodymium, praseodymium, dysprosium fluoride melts) and their corresponding oxides giving satisfactory results. The probe response varies for different electrolyte systems due to unique electrolyte properties such as diffusion coefficients of ion species, electrical conductivity, electrochemical reaction rates, and interfacial conditions (wetting of graphite electrode by electrolyte and gaseous products). Nevertheless, the character of response

is always similar which allows to accommodate the probe for use in many different conditions. Additionally, optimisation of the polarisation signal can significantly improve the response signal resolution and stability. Graphs in Figure 5 show the probe and temperature response during two additions of alumina to the low melting point electrolyte. Each addition contained 0.5 wt% of the total electrolyte mass. Non-filled circle points show probe data rescaled to Al_2O_3 concentration values based on a calibration curve. Solid square points show results of ex-situ oxygen analysis (recalculated to Al_2O_3 content) based on bath samples taken 5 minutes before and 5 min after each oxide addition. There is a rapid response of the probe after alumina addition: fast increase followed by plateau region indicating very fast kinetic of alumina dissolution under presented conditions. Most of added alumina portion was completely dissolved within approx. 2 minutes after addition. Alumina additions caused temperature decrease by approx. 3°C which is insignificant drop with minimal impact on the dissolution rate during test.

Figure 5 Probe and temperature response during additions of alumina in low temperature fluoride melt ($\text{NaF-AlF}_3\text{-KF}$).

The graphs presented in Figure 6 show the probe measurement and temperature change during additions of $\text{Nd}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Pr}_6\text{O}_{11}$ to the $\text{NdF}_3\text{-LiF}$ electrolyte. After each oxide addition there is a rapid increase in probe response indicating an initial fast dissolution rate for approximately 4 minutes followed by a slower increase in oxide concentration and finally a plateau which indicates complete dissolution of the added oxide. Similar to the previous example the temperature drops by approx. 4°C after oxide additions which is not expected to affect dissolution rate significantly.

Figure 6 Probe and temperature response during additions of an oxide mixture consisting of 77.5 wt% Nd_2O_3 and 22.5 wt% Pr_2O_3 in a neodymium and lithium fluoride melt (88.58 wt% NdF_3 and 11.42 wt% LiF).

Third example shows kinetic of dissolution of alumina in industrial grade electrolyte (Figure 7). Unlike the two previous examples, oxide addition was much larger, ca. 2.5 wt% of the total electrolyte mass was added in one batch. In this case, complete dissolution of the whole oxide addition took approximately 35 minutes which is significantly longer than in the previous cases. The longer period for the dissolution is probably due to a low dissolution rate resulting from the large bath temperature drop after the additions (ca. 8 °C drop in bath temperature). Also, the slow dissolution rate leads to sludge formation which sediments at the bottom of crucible. The stirring speed at 120 rpm used during the experiment was not sufficient to prevent the sludge formation. Alumina trapped in the sludge is more compacted hence transport of electrolyte to and from the alumina grains is substantially moderated. Such situation is very common during real operation of industrial cell where alumina is trapped in sludge or rafts caused by overfeeding or not optimal alumina distribution in cell. Presented example shows the importance of optimal oxide feeding to prevent the sludge formation for stable industrial cell operation.

Figure 7 Probe and temperature response during one addition of alumina in conventional industrial aluminium fluoride melt.

Conclusion and Outlook

The development of a probe for in-situ oxide concentration measurements in molten salts has been developed to give highly reliable results. The performance of the probe in laboratory scale has been verified based on three different electrolyte systems. The results show good probe response, signal to noise ratio and stability over time, revealing its potential as a useful tool for investigation of dissolution kinetics of oxides in various molten salt electrolytes. The technique and probe presented in this paper can be utilised for comparing the dissolution rates or kinetics of different oxide raw materials in different electrolyte systems. It can also be used for online monitoring of the oxide concentration during the electrolysis process.

The described measuring system was designed for laboratory use but can be adapted to perform measurements in industrial environment with minor changes, for instance to investigate distribution of oxide concentration in large cells. This can be a valuable tool to design better cells with optimal feeding points, hence, improving process operation in addition to reducing PFCs emissions.

Furthermore, industrial campaigns have been planned to test the probe in industrial settings. This will facilitate adaption of the probe for industrial applications.

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